

Bibliometric Analysis of Indonesia's Potential to Become the World Halal Industry Centre

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ABSTRACT

The concept of Shariah economy has been widely discussed in various countries around the world as an effort to achieve a sustainable economy, manifested in the halal industry. The high demand for halal products globally has led every country to strive to become a global provider of halal products, including Indonesia. With the largest Muslim population in the world, Indonesia aspires to become the center of the global halal industry. The aim of this research is to identify Indonesia's potential to become the center of the world's halal industry. The research method used is bibliometric analysis with a quantitative and qualitative approach. The results of this study depict Indonesia's potential to become the center of the global halal industry in terms of certified halal products, the number of halal certifications issued by various regions in Indonesia, and Indonesia's 2019-2023 master plan. Based on Indonesia's potential, the country is confident in becoming the center of the global halal industry.

ملخص

لقد حظي مفهوم الاقتصاد الشرعي باهتمام واسع في مختلف البلدان حول العالم، باعتباره من الجهود الرامية لتحقيق اقتصاد مستدام يتجسد في صناعة الحلال. وقد أدى ارتفاع الطلب العالمي على المنتجات الحلال إلى سعي كل بلد لتصبح مزودا عالميا لهذه المنتجات، بما في ذلك إندونيسيا. وباعتبارها البلد التي تضم أكبر عدد من المسلمين في العالم، تطمح إندونيسيا لأن تكون مركزا للصناعة الحلال العالمية. ويهدف هذا البحث إلى تحديد إمكانيات إندونيسيا في أن تصبح مركزا عالميا لصناعة الحلال. واستخدم في هذا البحث تحليل ببليومتري يجمع بين المنهج الكمي والنوعي. وأظهرت النتائج أن لإندونيسيا إمكانيات قوية لتكون مركز الصناعة الحلال العالمية، من حيث المنتجات الحلال المعتمدة، وعدد شهادات الحلال الصادرة من مختلف مناطقها، إضافة

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إلى الخطة الرئيسية 2019-2023 الخاصة بالصناعة الحلال. وبناء على هذه الإمكانيات، تُبدي إندونيسيا ثقة عالية في قدرتها على أن تصبح المركز العالمي لصناعة الحلال.

RÉSUMÉ

Le concept d'économie islamique (Shariah) a été largement débattu dans divers pays à travers le monde dans le cadre des efforts visant à mettre en place une économie durable, qui se manifeste notamment dans l'industrie halal. La forte demande mondiale en produits halal a incité tous les pays, y compris l'Indonésie, à s'efforcer de devenir un fournisseur mondial de produits halal. Avec la plus grande population musulmane au monde, l'Indonésie aspire à devenir le centre mondial de l'industrie halal. L'objectif de cette recherche est d'identifier le potentiel de l'Indonésie à devenir le centre mondial de l'industrie halal. La méthode de recherche utilisée est l'analyse bibliométrique avec une approche quantitative et qualitative. Les résultats de cette étude montrent le potentiel de l'Indonésie à devenir le centre de l'industrie halal mondiale en termes de produits certifiés halal, du nombre de certifications halal délivrées par différentes régions d'Indonésie et du plan directeur 2019-2023 de l'Indonésie. Compte tenu de son potentiel, l'Indonésie est confiante dans sa capacité à devenir le centre de l'industrie halal mondiale.

Keywords: Halal Industry, Halal Product, Muslims Country

JEL Classification: ART24080501

1. Introduction

In the midst of global economic uncertainty and the recovery of the global economy, the discussion of Islamic economy has become prominent in various countries (Abdul Ghafar Ismail & Noraziah Che Arshad, 2020; Abul A'la Mawdudi', 2020; Ahmed .F. EL-Ashker & Rodney Wilson, 2015; Baitul Hamdi & Tika Widyastuti, 2021; Ghozali et al., 2023; Havis Aravik et al., 2021; Suar et al., 2020a, 2020b; Ujang Syahrul & Izzani Ulfi, 2019). This is related to policy in economic recovery efforts. In light of this, many countries around the world are striving to develop the halal industry and become leading producers of halal products, including Indonesia. The Indonesian government is working towards developing the national halal industry and realizing the vision of "Indonesia as a Leading Halal Producer in the World." The State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2022 reveals that Indonesia's Islamic economic indicators

continue to improve, with Indonesia now ranking 4th in the world. Indonesia is one of the largest consumers of halal products globally, accounting for 11.34% of global halal expenditure (Erwansyah et al., 2024; Kasri et al., 2023; F. K. Rahman, 2022)

The rapidly increasing population of Muslims worldwide in recent years has also led to a growing awareness of the use of halal products (Albra et al., 2023; Septiani & Ridlwan, 2020). According to the Pew Research Center's Forum on Religion and Public Life, the global Muslim population is estimated to reach 2.2 billion people, or 26.5% of the total world population, by the year 2030 (Menko Airlangga, 2023). The increase in the Muslim population is not only from countries with a majority of Muslim inhabitants, but also from various European countries such as the United States, Australia, Germany, and others.

The increase in the global Muslim population has also led to a rise in demand for halal products (Aisyah et al., 2019; Nor et al., 2023) This demand encompasses a variety of products, including food, clothing, accommodation, tourism, and more. The high demand for halal products has led to countries competing to become the biggest suppliers of halal products, including Indonesia.

Indonesia is the country with the largest Muslim population in the world, with 236 million people, accounting for 12% of the world's Muslim population. As a result, there is high demand for halal products. However, Indonesia is still the world's largest consumer of halal products and has not yet fully tapped into its potential as a producer of halal products. This fact should encourage Indonesia to strive towards becoming a global halal producer. In addition to the high demand for halal products, Indonesia also has the natural resources and human capital to become a major player in the global halal industry (Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia et al., 2019).

In the halal food sector, Indonesia is the world's second-largest consumer, and in the halal cosmetics sector, it is the fourth-largest. According to the State of the Global Islamic Economic Report 2020-2021, the global Muslim consumer spending reached USD 2.02 trillion in the halal food, pharmaceutical, cosmetics, fashion, travel, and media/recreation sectors. The substantial demand for halal products, both domestically and internationally, has driven the Indonesian government to increase the

production of halal products. The hope is that Indonesia will be able to meet the demand for halal products both domestically and internationally.

Indonesia's commitment to becoming a leader in the global halal industry must be accompanied by serious efforts to create the best development strategies, such as improving the quality of SMEs and large companies that have successfully created halal products. This involves promoting human resources to develop halal industry businesses in various sectors, not just as consumers, providing interest-free Shariah financing for SMEs and all local halal industry producers (Adebayo & Salaudeen, 2021; Hameeda Batool Gillani et al., 2016; M. Rahman et al., 2024), as well as tapping into the potential natural resources owned by Indonesia to be managed into halal products. This will increase the motivation and spirit of the community to create innovative halal products for commercialization.

Human resources are crucial to the development of the halal industry (Sa'adah & Asnawi, 2022; Zuraidah & Mu'is, 2022). The individuals involved in developing halal products need to have a good understanding of the concept of halal according to Islamic principles, knowing what is permissible and what is not. Therefore, efforts should be made to enhance the understanding of human resources related to the halal industry.

In addition to developing human resources, the Indonesian government can establish special zones to accommodate all halal products for commercialization and to serve as a central hub for halal product transactions between countries.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Background Theory

The halal industry involves the processing of halal goods/services using raw materials, equipment, and processing methods permitted by Islamic law to produce halal products (Albra et al., 2023; Nor et al., 2023; Septiani & Ridlwan, 2020). The halal industry not only focuses on its products but also on consumers' lifestyle choices to consume halal food, which is beneficial for their health.

The State of the Global Islamic Economy Report (SGIER) 2022 states that several key sectors are supporting the global halal industry, including the halal food and beverage sector, halal pharmaceutical and cosmetic sector, Muslim-friendly tourism sector, and the modest fashion sector. Additionally, media and recreational activities are promoting the halal lifestyle, known as part of the creative economy sector in Indonesia.

To develop the halal industry and enhance Indonesia's economic growth, the Master Plan for Indonesian Halal Industry (MPIHI) is needed (Kementrian PPN/Bappenas, 2023). The MPIHI 2023-2029 carries the tagline "Halal Industry for Sustainable Economy," aligning with global economic developments and Indonesia's economic transformation as part of global participation for the future. The strengthening of MPIHI can be achieved through four main strategies: first, enhancing productivity and competitiveness; second, implementing and strengthening regulatory policies; third, strengthening finance and infrastructure; and fourth, strengthening halal branding and awareness."

2.2. Development of Halal Industry in Indonesia

The development of the halal industry in Indonesia is a transformation undertaken by the Indonesian government towards a sustainable economy in an effort to become a center of the global halal industry. Indonesia's efforts to become a center of the global halal industry are strongly supported by its potential (Adinugraha & Nadhifah, 2020). This potential includes its predominantly Muslim population, the availability of natural resources that can be used for Shariah-compliant tourism, Shariah-compliant hotels, a variety of food, medicines, and more (Bundo & Pratama, 2024; East et al., 2020; Faidah et al., 2021; Fauzi Ilyas et al., 2024; Jaelani, 2017; Ratnasari, 2020; Zaki et al., 2020).

The development of the Islamic economy and halal lifestyle is receiving attention from international communities of various countries. Not only from predominantly Muslim countries but also from non-Muslim countries such as those in Europe (Dinar Standard, 2020; Hastuti et al., 2023). Indonesia's population is predominantly Muslim, especially among the middle to lower class, which presents an opportunity for the development of the halal industry. The products produced can be sold domestically and exported abroad. According to the Indonesia Halal Market Report (IHMR) 2021/2022, Indonesia has the potential to add

USD 5.1 billion or IDR 72.9 trillion to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from sectors included in the halal industry (Ministry of PPN/Bappenas, 2023).

In developing the halal industry, Indonesia can focus on the processing industry, as this industry seeks to process materials that previously had no value or even low value, into high-value materials. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) recorded that the manufacturing sector contributed to the national GDP in 2022, amounting to 17.88%. Based on Ministry of Industry data (2022), the top two contributors from the manufacturing sector are the food and beverage industry (6.23%) and the chemical, pharmaceutical, and traditional medicine industry (1.74%). For example, processing fabric into clothes, processing flour into cakes, processing sugarcane into sugar, and so on, undoubtedly make the resulting processed materials more valuable.

Based on the survey conducted by KNKS in the National Strategy for the Development of the Halal Industry (2019), halal certification is a crucial consideration for producers (Noordin et al., 2014; Prabowo et al., 2015; Shuhada Abdul Basir et al., 2018). Therefore, the processing industry must pay attention to every step of the process, starting from sourcing raw materials, product design, production, storage, to product distribution. According to Law No. 33 of 2014 concerning Halal Product Assurance, halal products are produced through processes that ensure the halal status of the products, covering the sourcing of materials, processing, storage, packaging, distribution, sale, and presentations of the product.

2.3. Overview the Contribution of the Indonesian Halal Industry to Gross Domestic Product

The halal industry in Indonesia has contributed to the national income (Arifai, 2023; Jailani & Adinugraha, 2022; Mujahidin Mujahidin, 2020; Rangkyu, 2021a, 2021b; Susilawati, 2020; Yazid et al., 2020). For example, the tourism sector in Indonesia contributed 4.9% to the national economy in 2019. Despite the global tourism being heavily impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020, tourism in Indonesia still contributed 2.2% to the national economy, equivalent to IDR IDR 346 trillion, and was able to employ 21.3 million workers, which is about 16.2% of the national workforce in 2020.

Meanwhile, in other halal industry sectors, such as the creative economy, the recovery can be faster, despite experiencing an initial slowdown of -2.4% in 2020, followed by a growth of 2.9% in 2021. According to data released by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy (Kemenparekraf), the GDP of the creative economy contributed 7.0% to the national economy in 2021, amounting to IDR 1,191 trillion. This sector was able to employ 21.9 million workers, equivalent to 16.7% of the national workforce in 2021.

3. Methodology

The research utilized a systematic literature review with a bibliometric approach, known for statistical analysis using data from previous research (Nusair, 2019; Suban et al., 2021). Bibliometric analysis can be conducted transparently using quantitative and qualitative approaches to uncover knowledge. In this study, the researcher employed both quantitative and qualitative approaches through existing literature review. Bibliometrics were initially used to assist researchers in identifying and understanding the research networks of previous researchers based on citations, keywords, and authors. The data used by the researcher consisted of previous research findings, which were then systematically analyzed.

In this research, several steps were taken. First, the researcher selected the articles to be analyzed by using both inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion involved including the articles to be studied, while exclusion involved removing articles that were not used for analysis. Second, the researcher filtered the articles searched in Google Scholar by typing "halal industry in Indonesia" and "halal products in the provinces." The search using these keywords resulted in a total number of articles. Third, the articles were selected based on their content; if the research results revealed information about halal products in various provinces, then those articles were included for analysis. Process for obtaining data based on inclusion-exclusion method can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

4. Results and Analysis

From the search results that produced 11 analyzable articles (see table 1 below), we can observe the distribution of halal-certified products in various regions in Indonesia, ranging from beverages and food to hotels, tourism, lifestyle, and more. Each region in Indonesia has halal products that have obtained halal certification. The number of halal certifications issued by all provinces in Indonesia can be seen in table 2. To have an overview of the halal products owned by Indonesia, it can be seen in table 1."

Table 1. Overview of Halal Products Owned by Indonesia

Data resources	Title	Website (url)	Region	Types of halal product
Indonesian Journal of Halal (Susihono et al., 2018)	Tingkat Penggunaan Bahan Tersertifikasi Halal Berdasarkan Usulan Bidang Audit Kepada Tim Komisi Fatwa Mui Provinsi Banten	https://ejournal2.undip.ac.id/index.php/ijh/article/viewFile/3113/1953	Banten	Bread and Cake (bakery) 37.97%; snack group 17.62%; meat and processed meat products group 11.56%; Restaurant group 8.92% and catering group 6.57%.
Journal Keislaman, Kemasyarakatan dan Kebudayaan (Elsa Yolarita & Vivi Ukhwatul Khasanah Masbiran, 2022)	Analisis Faktor-Faktor Dalam Mengembangkan Pariwisata Halal Di Banten	https://jurnal.uin-banten.ac.id/index.php/tazkiya/article/view/4575/3225	Banten	Tourist destination for the heritage of the Sultanate of Banten, a place for historical relics from the time of the spread of Islam in Banten, as well as historical relics from the colonial period
Jurnal Hukumah: Jurnal Hukum Islam (Syukri Rosadi, 2023)	Potensi Pengembangan Wisata Halal Pelayanan Tambahan Di Masjid Agung Islamic Centre Rokan Hulu Untuk Meningkatkan	https://ojs.staituanikutambusai.ac.id/index.php/HUKUMAH/article/view/484/299	Kepulauan Riau	Grand Islamic Center Mosque, Rokan Hulu Regency

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Kesejahteraan Umat						
Dinas Kebudayaan dan Pariwisata Aceh (Israk Ahmadsyah et al., 2022)	Wisata Halal		https://repository.ar-raniry.ac.id/id/ep rint/28154/1/Buku%20Wisata%20Halal%20Aceh.pdf	Banda Aceh		Baiturrahman Grand Mosque, Baiturrahman Mosque, Al-Makmur Grand Mosque, . Haji Harun Keuchik Leumik Mosque, Kuala Syiah Cemetery, . Haji Harun Keuchik Leumik Mosque,
Journal Mahasiswa Kreatif (Syariah Hafidzoh, 2023)	Konsep Makanan Halal: Mie Gomak Medan Sebagai Kuliner Khas Sumatera Utara		REVISI+JMK+ Vol+1+No+4+Juli+2023+Hal+235-244.pdf	Sumatera Utara		Mie Gomak Noodles
Pengembangan Kawasan Industri Makanan Halal Di Sumatera Barat (Yolarita et al., 2022)	Pengembangan Kawasan Industri Makanan Halal Di Sumatera Barat		https://scholar.uinib.ac.id/id/eprint/1585/1/Penelitian_2022_Laporan_Akhir_Penelitian_Industri_Halal_Litbang.pdf	Sumatera Barat		Fish, Soybeans, Corn, Edible oils, Margarine, Soap, Cocoa Beans, Pasta, Cocoa snacks, Nuts, Seeds, Bananas, Rice, Vegetables, Fruit, Coconut oil, Milk, Meat, Skin, Tubers
LPPOM MUI Provinsi Jambi (LPPOM MUI Provinsi Jambi, 2015)	Daftar Produk Lokal yang Telah Tersertifikasi Halal		https://jambi.ke menag.go.id/file/201704250706329383375.pdf	Jambi		Spice, Catering, Meat, Chocolate, Ice cream, Processed Fish Products, Snacks, Pasta, Drinks, Cakes,

					Restaurants, Oil, Rice, Side dishes,
Kemenag Sumatera Selatan (LPPOM MUI Provinsi Jambi, 2015)	Daftar Nama Produk Bersertifikat Halal Sumatera Selatan	https://ppidsums.el.kemenag.go.id/datappid/daftar_namaprodukbersertifikathalal.pdf	Sumatera Selatan		Herbal Medicine, Cake, Tea, Pudding, Mpek-mpek, Cake, Pudding, Jelly, Chips, Peyek
Journal pengabdian masyarakat (Ahmad Farhan, 2018)	Pelaksanaan Sertifikasi Halal Lppom Mui Terhadap Produk Usaha Mikro, Kecil Dan Menengah (Umkm) (Studi Lppom Mui Provinsi Bengkulu)	2340-5637-1-PB.pdf	Bengkulu		Meatballs, Bread and Sponge Cakes, Restaurants, bottled drinking water. Coffee and tea drinks
Journal Masharif al-Syariah: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Perbankan Syariah (Muhammad Iqbal Fasa, 2019)	Role Model Bisnis Halal Lampung Dalam Meningkatkan Halal Tourism Di Provinsi Lampung (Studi Empiris Pada Coffee Shop Dr. Koffie Provinsi Lampung)	mimin,+11_fasa.pdf	Lampung		Lampung coffe
Journal Pemberdayaan Masyarakat: Media Pemikiran	The Promotion of Halal Tourism in Bangka Belitung: The	dakwahjournal,+Journal+manager,+7+-+Febri.pdf	Bangka Belitung		Hotels, tourism, restaurants

dan Dakwah Development of
 Pembangunan Potential Asset
 (Yanasari, 2021) and Local
 Enterprises
 Players

After reviewing various halal products in Indonesia across different regions, we can see that Indonesia's halal products come from various sectors, not only in the form of food and beverages, but also in tourism, accommodation, mosques, historical Islamic sites, restaurants, tombs, and more. The review shows that the highest number of halal-certified products is in the food and beverage sector. Therefore, in the future, Indonesia can focus on encouraging SMEs and large companies producing halal-certified food to advance internationally, urging businesses to innovate and create certified halal products. The government can also encourage the younger generation to have a business mindset in creating new things that support the growth of halal products. This has the potential to make Indonesia a hub for the global halal industry. The table in Figure 3 shows the number of halal certifications held by Indonesia from different regions.

Table 3: Number of Halal Certification Issuance by Product Type, Source (Ministry of Religious Affairs, Republic of Indonesia, 2021)

Province	Food and beverage	Catering and Restaurant	Cosmetic and medicine	Building goods	Services	Biology Products
Abroad	600		13	5	4	
Aceh	382		30	0	0	
North Sumatera utara	971		32	1	2	
West Sumatera	1966		32	0	1	
Riau	1.540		4	6	1	
Jambi	998		14	0	1	

South Sumatera	1571	4	1	1
Bengkulu	400	160	0	0
Lampung	10.868	4	0	2
Bangka Belitung Islands	522	23	0	0
Riau Islands	1.239	224	1	4
DKI Jakarta	6.333	409	37	23
West Java	19.770	375	48	21
Central Java	18.386	120	11	13
DI Yogyakarta	3.678	405	1	1
East Java	22.691	158	34	12
Banten	3.954	19	30	21
Bali	303	11	1	0
West Nusa Tenggara	662	1	0	0
East Nusa tenggara	98	10	0	0
West Kalimantan	427	22	0	0
Central Kalimantan	577	10	0	0
South Kalimantan	970	8	1	0
East Kalimantan	1.014	0	0	1

North Kalimantan	126		1	0	0	
North Sulawesi	131		9	0	3	
Central Sulawesi	925		15	0	0	
South Sulawesi	1.493		1	0	0	
Southeast Sulawesi	237		2	0		
Gorontalo	293		5	0		
West Sulawesi	509		7	0		
Maluku	154		1	0		
North Maluku	220		0	0		
Papua	52		0	0		
West Papua	33		105	0		
Central	3.681	372	812	42	1	2

Based on the review of the number of certified halal products, East Java occupies the first position with the highest number of halal-certified products at 22,691. The second highest is West Java with 19,770 products, and the third highest is Central Java with 18,368. From the above data, it is evident that the distribution of halal products is still uneven, with the production of certified halal products predominantly concentrated in Java. Therefore, there is a need to promote more even distribution by encouraging innovation in producing certified halal products in regions outside of Java, particularly in Aceh, also known as the "veranda of Mecca." This should serve as motivation for them to create halal products.

Indonesia's effort to become a global halal industry producer, it must have precise designs and analyses to serve as the foundation for developing the

halal industry in various fields and sectors. This will ensure that Indonesia's potential in becoming the global center for the halal industry is realized. It is important to have a well-measured and well-conceived plan to achieve this goal. Below, the researcher will describe the master plan for Indonesia's halal industry for the years 2023-2029.

Figure 2. Framework for the Indonesian Halal Industry Master Plan

Sumber : Kajian Roadmap Industri Halal (dimodifikasi), Bank Indonesia

Based on the master plan in the diagram above, Indonesia is showing its commitment to becoming the global center for halal product manufacturing. We can see the step-by-step approach planned by the government to achieve this. In the initial stage starting in 2023, Indonesia aims to raise awareness among the public about halal products. Once public awareness about halal products and the halal lifestyle improves, people will naturally consume halal products and adopt a halal lifestyle. In 2024, Indonesia aims to become the global center for halal product manufacturing through further development. In 2025/2026, Indonesia plans to build a global value chain network. By 2027/2028, Indonesia aims to become the global halal center. Finally, in 2029, Indonesia aims to establish a global halal brand.

5. Conclusion

The conclusion of this article is that Indonesia has great potential to become the world's center for the halal industry. The significant potential can be seen from: first, the availability of a wide variety of halal products from various regions that have been halal certified, the large number of

halal certifications issued by each region, and the master plan that Indonesia has in place until 2029.

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